

Top Trending Market Penetration by Startups

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The sudden boom for startups in the market is not a coincidence. There are many startups today than ever before. Dynamic markets, uncertain and overwhelming circumstances have encouraged smaller players to take risks and actually turn out successful. Essentially, such risks would be a huge gamble for large organizations due to the lack of guaranteed returns.

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Entrepreneurs on the other hand, are willing to take the challenge as they are better acquainted to the “winner takes all” philosophy. There is also the advantage of flexibility, not having to deal with bureaucracy, better team chemistry and the benefit of competitive pricing. Often start-ups focus on niche markets and once they breakeven, they are able to successfully build a dominant presence for themselves in the industry.

Below are a few niche markets that continues to remain lucrative to the IT startup sector.

Internet of Things IOT

The possibilities in this sector is immense, beginning with smart systems, connected homes and devices to complicated ecosystems linking entire cities. The IoT is a hot and blooming sector. Startups have the advantage of being the early adopters to the latest in technology and hence gain the upper hand. A large number **Startup IT service providers** work on IoT services and IoT development projects that will soon be touching our lives in a whole new way. The major areas that are seeing digital disruption are IoT healthcare, Industries and automotive. IoT cloud services have also found immense relevance as, it has a pivotal role to play in terms of connecting various devices with the relevant data enabling devices to perform without human intervention. Some of the trending IoT services and IoT solutions are provided by StartUps further affirming that the startup ecosystem is the most conducive for technology adaptation. As an IT and product development company, we at Gateway provide Startups the necessary platform and solutions which will back them up to successfully develop, deploy and maintain IoT Solutions/Products.

Microsoft Technologies

Once upon a time Microsoft Technologies were the only solutions that were reliable in the market. That was until the huge technology shift towards mobility and mobility solutions. After falling out in the race, Microsoft has made a huge comeback and today the Microsoft stack is one of the most reliable technology. Startups are quick to adapt to these changes and find a place in most Startup development projects. Below are a few popular ones.

–**Azure**– Just as Microsoft claims you can “get more done” through Azure. It is an integrated tool that lets you make the most of cloud services, avail analytics, use a

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powerful database; and deliver complex mobile, networking, storage and web solutions. Here's what Azure can give you

- Build and manage Enterprise solutions
- Design and develop Mobility and mobile solutions
- Create apps that tap into the IoT
- Leverage Microsoft's Cloud Storage Services

– **Dynamics** – Microsoft Dynamics is an enterprise resource planning and customer relationship management software development platform. The Microsoft dynamics business solutions empowers businesses with real-time data and collaboration tools making them better equipped to make crucial decisions. This suite provides a complete business solution for its clients through the Microsoft Dynamics Nav, Microsoft Dynamics AR and Microsoft Dynamics CRM solutions. As a competent Microsoft technologies service provider, we design and build efficient ERP and CRM solutions for businesses enabling them to promote productivity and collaboration at any place to any device.

– **.Net**– .Net has been around for a while now, that is perhaps why it is one of the best programming frameworks. Startups have been making the most of this infrastructure through .Net application development services to build and deploy applications that run on the framework. These technologies have been used by organizations small and large to create complex and large applications to meet specific business requirements.

– **SharePoint** – SharePoint consulting, customization, SharePoint migration and other development services on this robust collaboration platform is trending these days and startups have been fast to pick up on this. The recent announcements of sandbox deprecation and improved office tools have called for SharePoint migration and SharePoint consulting services that give business owners better flexibility and control.

Product engineering

Most startups have penetrated the Product design & development market in both IT and Non IT sectors. However, this segment has seen both Startups and larger companies contribute as it is a trend that calls for innovation. At Gateway Technolabs GmbH, we have been assisting startups in successfully designing, developing and deploying products that they envision. When you hire Product development services the product design & development include technology consulting, development & deployment,

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maintenance solutions, etc. Besides working on new projects, the dynamic technology landscape also calls for technology upgrades and product migrations. The huge opportunities that the technologies of today offer, have provided prospects that pave the way for creative innovation.

Gateway Technolabs GmbH is an IT consultant company that focuses on creating technology solutions that impact our lives in a positive manner. The company has been supporting and empowering StartUps in this endeavor. With a good presence in the European and central European markets, we continue to deliver incomparable services.

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